

THE EFFECT OF ETHICAL PRACTICES AND COMPETENCE OF AUDITORS ON AUDIT ASSURANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11400688>

ABSTRACT

This paper examined the effect of Ethical Practices and Competence of Auditor on Audit Assurance. The respondents were twenty (20) Certified Public Accountants from different auditing firms in General Santos City, selected using the random sampling method. The researchers used an adapted-modified standardized questionnaire. The data were analyzed using mean, Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and Multiple Regression. The extent that the auditors observed ethical practices obtained the grand mean result of 4.59, interpreted as very extensive. Regarding the level of competence of the auditors, it attained the grand mean result of 4.32, interpreted as high. Meanwhile, the level of audit assurance provided by the auditor in an audit obtained the overall mean of 4.65, interpreted as very high. The results suggested that the ethical practices had a significant relationship with audit assurance. While the competence of the auditor had no significant relationship with audit assurance. Overall, both ethical practices and competence of the auditor did not seem to have a statistically significant influence on audit assurance at 0.05 significance level in this analysis. Consequently, it was advised to utilize this study as the foundation for investigating similar studies with other variables that influence audit assurance.

Keywords: *Ethical Practices, Competence of Auditor, Audit Assurance*

INTRODUCTION

External auditors have provided verification and assurance audit services. They significantly contributed to enhancing the informational quality for decision-makers. Their objective was to enhance and improve the quality of audits and boost investor confidence in the financial statement. Auditors placed a greater emphasis on adhering to the code of ethics and increasing their skills to regain the trust of the public (Alsughayer, 2021). Professional accountants must have integrity, objectivity, and independence in addition to a sufficient degree of competence to carry out their ethical standards, which they should utilize as a guide in conducting the audit procedures (Todorovic, 2018).

There were several high-profile cases involving unethical accounting practices posing the importance of the auditing profession. Kotb et al. (2020) observed in their study that a lack of professional ethics generally contributed to the ineffectiveness of quality assurance in the financial sector auditing of accounts. Furthermore, there had been growing concern about the ethical issues in the auditing profession regarding questionable acts such as corporate failures and ethical negligence (Ezeagba & Abiahu, 2018).

The problems mentioned shed light on the factuality that ethical auditing principles must be upheld to the highest degree at all times, as well as the professional competence of the auditors. This was to ensure that the auditing profession maintained its critical role in ensuring the accuracy and reliability of the financial statements. These issues raised concerns about the effectiveness and integrity of the auditing profession posing challenges to auditors, businesses, and society as a whole. The Code of Ethics made and approved by the International Federation of Accountants and the Board of Accountancy in the Philippines both stated that professional accountants, especially external auditors, should comply with the fundamental principles of ethics in carrying out their work. With this, auditors could provide an independent and unbiased opinion on the fairness and accuracy of financial statements.

The study of Setyowati et al. (2021) found out that auditors dared to disclose things according to their considerations and beliefs needed to be done when performing audit tasks in accordance with facts, did not find fault or hide mistakes, and maintained honesty and obeyed rules in performing audit tasks. Meanwhile, Kertarajasa et al. (2019) discovered that knowledgeable and trained auditors would have a broader view of auditing and could spot irregularities in the financial records. Moreover, to produce a quality audit report, the auditor must be equipped with proper knowledge and experience to perform the audit tasks. As a result, a high level of competence could improve the audit quality. Incompetency would likely lead to relying on others' opinions as to the conduct of the audit tasks which could weaken the audit quality. The result deduced that having a skilled auditor in charge of the audit engagement was critical to the effectiveness and efficiency of the audit.

According to Lubis (2021), the objectivity variable had an effect that was significant on the audit quality results, which could be seen from the statistical t-value of 5.011 and a p-value of 0.000. Because the t-value was greater than 2.00 and the p-value. The result

showed that the higher the level of objectivity of the auditor, the better the audit quality. The auditing standards stated that by adhering to the principle of objectivity, the auditor was expected to be honest at all times and not be influenced by any party while carrying out audit engagement. It indicated that the fair presentation of audit reports prepared by the auditor and avoidance of biases in discharging their responsibility influences the overall quality of audit assurance. Additionally, the paper of Adekoya et al. (2020) presumed that the innate factors of the auditors had a vital role in ascertaining the behavior of the auditor in examining the book of accounts of its clients and expressing an audit opinion of it. Thus, being terrified of the penalties, religious norms, gender, conscience, innate values, and upbringing of auditors working in audit firms helped determine how their actions ultimately influence the performance and position of the audit firm.

Transferable skills are talents that are used across areas. These skills were crucial for the development of human resources. Skills for learning, employment and entrepreneurship, personal growth, and active citizenship were among the competencies listed. These were interconnected skills that could improve learning outcomes, compel students to attend class, foster responsibility, and open doors to better work in the future (Nambiar et al., 2019). Moreover, the study of Mardan and Hussain (2023) stated that the professional abilities of an individual were the qualities that were acquired, hereditary, and inherent. It also stated that the performance efficiency of a person was his true action, considering that the action was performed within the framework of values, professional attitudes, and ethics, and complied with professional responsibility to protect the public interest.

Alsughayer (2021) investigated the impact of the competence of the auditor on the quality of their audit in his research study. This related study then revealed a mean score of between 4.30 and 3.95, which was considered to be very high. This result indicated that a large proportion of participants recognized the importance and positive impact of auditor competence on the quality of audits. Furthermore, this related study revealed that most of its respondents agreed that when it comes to auditor competence, knowledge, continuous improvement and training, professional experience and certification, and educational qualifications all have a significant impact on the quality of audits. This empirical evidence resulted in the conclusion that the auditor's competence had a direct correlation with the quality of the audit. Likewise, according to the study of Pinto et al. (2020), the competence of the auditors, based on their knowledge, continuous improvement, training, ability to acquire professional experience and certification, and education, had a significant impact on the quality of the audit. Moreover, Tarmidi et al. (2019) stated that the auditor's expertise and impartiality enabled investors to view the results of their opinions on the financial statements of the company to be more accurate and informative. High-quality audits, particularly those conducted by external parties, render financial reports trustworthy, as they are not subject to the influence of management.

The study of Alkebbsee et al. (2021) found that there was a correlation between the quality of audit assurance and the professional ethics considering the result $12.52 > 1.96$ at a 5% level of significance. Moreover, Haeridistia and Fadjarenie (2019) stated that the professional ethics of the auditors affected the audit quality as audit results would be in

accordance with the conditions of the actual financial statements if they always implemented the professional code of ethics. It is through ethical conduct that auditors can ensure that the financial statements provided to stakeholders are accurate and reliable. Therefore, adherence to professional ethics could enhance the reputation of the audit profession and foster public trust. The incorporation of professional ethics in the audit assurance process could significantly enhance the quality of financial reporting and promote ethical behavior in the financial sector.

The study conducted by Pinto et al. (2020) concluded that the auditors' competence had a significant impact on the audit quality. On the contrary, according to the study of Kusumawati and Syamsuddin (2018), the competence of the auditor did not have a direct effect on the audit quality. Additionally, Putri and Nengzih (2021) determined that the audit quality was not significantly affected by competence. Moreover, Ramlah et al. (2018) conducted a study that obtained a conclusion that the competency of the auditors had a major influence on audit quality. The relationship between audit assurance and auditor competency was essential for ensuring that the audit was conducted effectively and the audit assurance provided was reliable. The goal of the auditing process was to gather sufficient and appropriate audit evidence that supported the evaluation of the auditor on the financial statement. As they were better equipped to identify and assess risks connected to the financial statements, specifically the internal control system of the client, auditors that were competent were required for expert judgments. According to auditing standards, auditors must be competent to carry out the audit engagements successfully, which includes having the requisite technical training, competence, and industry-specific knowledge.

According to the study conducted by Kertarajasa et al. (2019), the auditor ethics and competence did not have a significant effect on audit quality because of the overpowering external factors, specifically when the superiors intervened in the audit process. On the other hand, Asry (2021) concluded that the competence and ethics of auditors had a simultaneous effect on the audit quality.

Therefore, the researchers of this study were interested in the ethical practices observed by auditors as well as how the competence of auditors could affect audit assurance. The focus of this research was to provide an overview in determining the significant relationship between the ethical practices and competence of auditors on audit assurance. This was to obtain the level of auditor assessment at General Santos City in terms of the performance of the auditors.

Research Questions

This study sought to identify the effect of the ethical practices and the competence of auditors on audit assurance. It focused on the auditing services provided by the Certified Public Accountants (CPAs) in General Santos City.

1. To what extent did auditors observe ethical practices in terms of:
 - 1.1. Integrity;
 - 1.2. Professional Competence and Due Care;
 - 1.3. Objectivity; and
 - 1.4. Professional Behavior?

2. What was the level of competence of the auditors in terms of:
 - 2.1. Transferable Skills; and,
 - 2.2. Audit Skills?
3. What was the level of audit assurance provided by the auditor in an audit?
4. Was there a significant relationship between the extent of the ethical practices of auditors and the level of audit assurance they provided?
5. Was there a significant relationship between the competence of auditors and the level of audit assurance they provided?
6. Did the ethical practices and competence of auditors have a significant effect on the audit assurance they provided?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This research study was conducted in randomly selected auditing and accounting firms located at General Santos City. The City of General Santos, abbreviated as GenSan, is a 1st class highly urbanized coastal city in the Philippine Islands located in Region 12. It was geographically situated in South Cotabato Province.

Research Design

This study was a quantitative descriptive study as it described the relationship between the ethical practices and competence of auditors on audit assurance in General Santos City. This was a non-experimental study since the variables collected were measured numerically. The variables were not altered by the researchers. The researchers evaluated the effect of ethical practices and the competence of auditors on audit assurance.

Respondents

This research study utilized a simple random sampling method in choosing the respondents who were the Certified Public Accountants (CPAs) in different public practice firms who provided auditing services in General Santos City. The respondents were at least accredited by the regulatory bodies that provided accreditation for CPAs in the Philippines, such as the Board of Accountancy (BOA), Business of Internal Revenue (BIR), Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas (BSP), Cooperative Development Authority (CDA), and Insurance Commission (IC).

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering data and information, the steps undertaken by the researchers were the following:

First, the researchers prepared an adapted, modified, and standardized questionnaire that was applicable to the research study. Then, it underwent a validation process with

the help of the experts to ensure the credibility and reliability of the adapted and modified questionnaire.

Second, the researchers asked permission from the Institution for authorization to conduct the study.

Third, the researchers sent a letter to the Local Government Unit (LGU) of General Santos City in order to obtain the lists of the auditing firms in the said city. The researchers then provided a letter of permission to the auditing firms and managers for the administration of the study. When given permission, the researchers provided a letter of invitation and a research survey questionnaire.

Lastly, at the end of the survey, the answered questionnaires were immediately encoded in Microsoft Excel using a tally graph. The data was summarized and treated with appropriate statistical tools. Then, the researchers interpreted the results and made conclusions and recommendations upon receiving the data collection results.

Research Instrument

The study utilized an adapted, modified, and standardized questionnaire constructed based on the works Morton (1998) and Susanto et al. (2022) tailored to ensure the consistency of the responses of the respondents. The questionnaire was composed of three parts arranged in accordance with the sequence of the variables. Parts one, two, and three utilized a 5-point Likert scale to measure the extent to which a respondent agreed or disagreed with a statement. The scale had five response options, ranging from 5-strongly agree to 1-strongly disagree. The Likert scale allowed for the quantitative analysis, interpretation of the data, and provided insights into the of the respondent's responses to the statements.

Data Analysis

This study utilized statistical instruments to analyze the information collected for the research. Mean was utilized to analyze the data that measured the extent auditors observed ethical practices, as well as the level of competence of the auditors and audit assurance they provided in an audit. Additionally, Pearson Correlation Coefficient or Pearson R was used to evaluate the significant relationship between the ethical practices of the auditors and the audit assurance they provided, and the significant relationship between the competence of the auditors and the audit assurance they provided. Lastly, Multiple Regression was utilized to examine the significant relationship between the two independent variables on the dependent variable which was the significant effect of ethical practices and competence of auditors on audit assurance.

Scope and Limitations

This study investigated the effect of ethical practices and competence of auditors on audit assurance provided by the CPAs who worked in auditing firms in General Santos City. This study was limited to the CPAs who provided auditing services from the auditing firms in General Santos City. The researchers identified the accessible and available auditing firms in General Santos City and randomly selected the CPAs who provided auditing services within these firms. The study did not account for the influence of environmental

factors that could affect the ethical practices and competence of the auditors, such as the organizational culture and the regulatory environment of the firm of the auditors. The study was limited to the independent CPAs who were at least registered and accredited by the BOA Accreditations of CPAs Philippines, BIR Accreditation of CPAs Philippines, SEC Accreditation of CPAs Philippines, BSP Accreditation of CPAs Philippines, CDA Accreditation of CPAs Philippines, and other accreditation of CPAs government agencies.

RESULTS

The Extent Auditors Observed Ethical Practices in Terms of Integrity

Table 1.1
The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices in Terms of Integrity

Items	Mean	Description
1. I am straightforward and honest in all business professional dealings.	4.60	Strongly Agree
2. I conduct myself in a way that is above suspicion and reproach to keep the public's trust.	4.75	Strongly Agree
3. I present the audit information fully, honestly, and professionally.	4.75	Strongly Agree
4. I do not allow my integrity to be called into question.	4.80	Strongly Agree
5. I adhere to the high ethical standards in the course of my work and in my relationship whether it be personal or with the staff of audited entities.	4.90	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.76	Strongly Agree

Table 1.1 showed that the auditors adhered to the high ethical standards in the course of their work and their relationships whether it be personal or with staff of audited entities. This gained the highest mean of 4.90 which was interpreted as very extensive. Moreover, auditors not allowing their integrity to be called into question gained the second-highest mean of 4.80 which was interpreted as very extensive. Finally, auditors' straightforwardness and honesty in all of their business professional dealings gained the lowest mean of 4.60, interpreted as very extensive. Overall, the auditors observed ethical practices in terms of integrity with an overall mean of 4.76 verbally described as strongly agree and interpreted as very extensive.

The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices in Terms of Professional Competence and Due Care

Table 1.2
The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices
in Terms of Professional Competence and Due Care

Items	Mean	Description
1. I only undertake work for which I am competent and qualified.	4.40	Agree
1. I exercise professional skepticism in the audit process.	4.75	Strongly Agree
2. I follow applicable technical and professional standards when providing services.	4.70	Strongly Agree
3. I possess the necessary knowledge, education, and experience appropriate to perform auditing services.	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. I continually strive to maintain and improve my proficiency, effectiveness, skills, and knowledge.	4.65	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.61	Strongly Agree

Table 1.2 revealed that the auditors' strong agreement that they exercised professional skepticism in their audit processes obtained the highest mean of 4.75, interpreted as very extensive. Furthermore, auditors following the applicable technical and professional standards diligently gained the second highest mean of 4.70, interpreted as very extensive. Lastly, auditors' agreement that they only undertook the works in which they were competent and qualified obtained the lowest mean of 4.40, interpreted as highly extensive. All in all, the extent to which the auditors observed ethical practices in terms of professional competence and due care obtained an overall mean score of 4.61, interpreted as very extensive.

The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices in Terms of Objectivity

Table 1.3
The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical
Practices in Terms of Objectivity

Items	Mean	Description
1. I do not place myself in positions in which I have or could have conflict of interest.	4.40	Agree
2. I do not allow bias or the undue influence of others to compromise my professional judgment.	4.65	Strongly Agree

3. I am fair, impartial, and intellectually honest.	4.50	Strongly Agree
4. I perform all professional work with an objective mind.	4.60	Strongly Agree
5. When I know someone who has a conflict of interest, I disclose the conflict to those involved.	4.25	Agree
Overall Mean	4.48	Agree

Based on Table 1.3, auditors' strong agreement on not allowing bias or undue influence of others to compromise their professional judgment gained the highest mean of 4.65, interpreted as very extensive. Notably, auditors performing professional work with an objective mindset attained the second-highest mean of 4.60, interpreted as very extensive. Meanwhile, auditors disclosing conflicts to those involved when they know someone who had a conflict of interest obtained the lowest mean of 4.25, interpreted as highly extensive. The extent to which the auditors observed ethical practices in terms of objectivity got an overall mean score of 4.48, interpreted as highly extensive.

The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices in Terms of Professional Behavior

Table 1.4
The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices
in Terms of Professional Behavior

Items	Mean	Description
1. I comply with relevant laws and regulations and refrain from any conduct which might bring discredit the audit profession.	4.85	Strongly Agree
2. I dress appropriately during the auditing process.	4.15	Agree
3. I behave in a manner consistent with the good reputation of the audit profession.	4.60	Strongly Agree
4. I am professional in my conduct and speech. I do not use profanity.	4.30	Agree
5. I behave with courtesy and consideration towards all with whom I come into contact with during the audit process.	4.55	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.49	Agree
Grand Mean Result:	4.59	Strongly Agree

In this section, auditors' compliance with relevant laws and regulations and avoidance of any conduct that could bring discredit to their audit profession obtained the highest mean of 4.85, interpreted as very extensive. Likewise, auditors behaving in a manner consistent

with the good reputation of the audit profession gained the second highest mean of 4.60, interpreted as very extensive. Meanwhile, auditors dressing appropriately during the auditing process got the lowest mean of 4.15, interpreted as highly extensive. The findings indicated that the extent to which the auditors observe ethical practices in terms of professional behavior obtained an overall mean of 4.49, interpreted as highly extensive. Overall, the grand mean result of the extent to which auditors observed ethical practices was 4.59, interpreted as very extensive.

The Level of Competence of Auditors in Terms of Transferable Skills

Table 2.1
The Level of Competence of the Auditors
in Terms of Transferable Skills

Items	Mean	Description
1. I am able to network easily with other people.	4.25	Agree
2. I am able to express myself clearly and concisely to a group of people.	4.30	Agree
3. I am able to remain calm and to claim others.	4.15	Agree
4. I am able to build to a rapport with others.	4.30	Agree
5. I am able to manage and prioritize time to meet deadlines.	4.20	Agree
6. I am able to avoid distractions.	3.75	Agree
7. I am able to update deadlines based on changing circumstances.	4.40	Agree
8. I am able to gather information in a systematic way to establish certain facts.	4.40	Agree
9. I am able to reflect and critique my own performance.	4.35	Agree
10. I am able to reach a mutually satisfactory outcome through compromise.	4.25	Agree
Overall Mean	4.24	Agree

Table 2.1 showed that the auditors' agreement on updating the deadlines based on the changing circumstances and gathering information in a systematic way to establish certain facts; both got the highest weighted mean of 4.40, interpreted as high. Notably, the auditors' reflection and critique of their own performance got the second highest mean of 4.35, interpreted as high. Meanwhile, the auditors' ability to avoid distractions obtained the lowest mean of 3.75, interpreted as high. Overall, it showed that the level of competence of auditors in terms of transferable skills obtained an overall mean of 4.24, interpreted as high, indicating their competency in these critical competencies. These skills contributed to the auditors' effectiveness and performance in their responsibilities, emphasizing the importance of these skills in the auditing industry.

The Level of Competence of Auditors in Terms of Audit Skills

Table 2.2
The Level of Competence of the Auditors
in Terms of Audit Skills

Items	Mean	Description
1. I understand the operational processes of the audited entity.	4.35	Agree
2. I sought information on laws and regulations related to the entity's operations.	4.60	Strongly Agree
3. I study the management policies of the audited entity.	4.55	Strongly Agree
4. I profile the internal and external environment and stakeholders of the audited entity.	4.35	Agree
5. I study the organizational structure, budget and realization, internal implementation guidelines, and operational guidelines of the entity.	4.40	Agree
6. I validate the reliability of the audit evidence.	4.50	Strongly Agree
7. I attend seminars/training on audits.	4.30	Agree
8. I understand the initial information of the case to be audited.	4.45	Agree
9. I have the ability to study problems quickly.	4.30	Agree
10. I profile the internal and external environment and stakeholders of the entity to be audited.	4.30	Agree
Overall Mean	4.41	Agree
Grand Mean Result	4.32	Agree

Table 2.2 revealed that auditors seeking information on laws and regulations related to the entity's operations obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.60, interpreted as very high. Likewise, auditors studying the management policies of the audited entity attained the second-highest mean of 4.55, interpreted as very high. Moreover, auditors attending seminars/training on audits, studying problems quickly, and profiling the internal and external environment and stakeholders of the audited entity gained the lowest mean of 4.30, interpreted as high. Overall, it showed that the level of competence of auditors in terms of audit skills obtained an overall mean of 4.41, interpreted as high. The level of competence of auditors achieved an impressive grand mean result of 4.32, interpreted as high.

The Level of Audit Assurance provided by the Auditor in an Audit

Table 3
The Level of Audit Assurance Provided by the Auditor in an Audit

Items	Mean	Description
1. The audit assurance I provide is free from material fraud.	4.65	Strongly Agree
2. The audit assurance I provide is free from material illegal acts.	4.55	Strongly Agree
3. The audit assurance I provide is free from material judgment errors.	4.60	Strongly Agree
4. The audit assurance I provide is free from material human-error other than judgment errors.	4.45	Agree
5. The audit assurance I provide is based on an objective examination of audit facts and findings.	4.70	Strongly Agree
6. The audit assurance I provide is presented in an effective manner.	4.55	Strongly Agree
7. The audit assurance I provide is impartial and free from any conflict of interest with the company.	4.70	Strongly Agree
8. The audit assurance I provide protects and preserves the interests of stakeholders.	4.75	Strongly Agree
9. The audit assurance I provide is prepared in conformity with auditing standards and principles.	4.80	Strongly Agree
10. The audit assurance I provide is based on an honest expression of opinion.	4.75	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	4.65	Strongly Agree

Based on the gathered data, auditors' strong agreement that the audit assurance they provided was prepared in conformity with auditing standards and principles got the highest mean of 4.80, interpreted as very high. Notably, the auditors' strong agreement that their audit assurance protected and preserved the stakeholders' interest and was based on an honest expression of opinion attained the second-highest mean of 4.75, interpreted as very high. Lastly, the auditors' agreement that they provide an audit assurance that was free from material human-error other than judgment errors obtained the lowest mean of 4.45, interpreted as high. The overall mean result of the level of audit assurance provided by the auditor was 4.65, interpreted as very high.

Significant Relationship between the Ethical Practices of Auditors and Audit Assurance

Table 4
Significant Relationship between the Ethical Practices of Auditors and Audit Assurance

Variable	Audit Assurance		
	R-value	p-value	Remarks
Ethical Practices of Auditors	0.525	0.018	Significant

The statistical analysis revealed an R-value of 0.525 with a p-value of 0.018. This indicated a statistically significant positive relationship between the extent of ethical practices and audit assurance. In other words, as auditors engage in more ethical practices, they tend to have a higher quality of audit assurance. Based on these findings, it was appropriate to reject the null hypothesis (H_01), suggesting the presence of a significant relationship between ethical practices and audit assurance. The findings from Table 4 suggested that ethical practices among auditors had a significant positive relationship with audit assurance.

Significant Relationship between the Competence of Auditors and Audit Assurance

Table 5
Significant Relationship between the Competence of Auditors and Audit Assurance

Variable	Audit Assurance		
	R-value	p-value	Remarks
Competence of Auditors	0.394	0.088	Not Significant

The statistical analysis in this case yielded an R-value of 0.394 and a p-value of 0.086. The p-value was above the commonly used significance threshold of 0.05. Therefore, there was no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis (H_02), implying that the competence of the auditor did not have a statistically significant relationship with the level of audit assurance that they provided in their auditing services.

Significant Effect of Ethical Practices and Competence of Auditors on Audit Assurance

Table 6
Significant Influence of Ethical Practices and Competence of Auditors on Audit Assurance

Independent variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.366	1.295		1.055	.306
Ethical	.760	.451	.556	1.685	.110
Competence	-.046	.376	-.040	-.123	.904
Multiple r: 0.525 r-squared: 0.276 f-value: 3.242 Sig /p-value: 0.064					

In this analysis, the dependent variable was the audit assurance provided by the auditor, meanwhile, the independent variables were the ethical practices and competence of the auditors.

Looking at the coefficients, it could be observed that the constant term is 1.366 with a standard error of 1.295. This indicated an expected audit assurance when both ethical practices and competence were zero. However, it was important to note that this constant was not statistically significant since the associated p-value is 0.306, which was greater than the commonly used significance level of 0.05.

Moving on to the independent variables, ethical practices had an unstandardized coefficient of 0.760, a standard error of 0.451, and a beta (standardized coefficient) of 0.556. This suggested the presence of a positive relationship between ethical practices and audit assurance. This relationship was moderately strong. However, the associated t-statistic was 1.685, and the p-value was 0.110. While the beta suggested a positive influence, the p-value indicated that this relationship was not statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level, suggesting that the effect of ethical practices on audit assurance may not be strong enough to draw firm conclusions.

Conversely, when examining the competence of auditors, the researchers found an unstandardized coefficient of -0.046, a standard error of 0.376, and a beta of -0.040. This indicated a negative relationship between auditor competence and audit assurance and the relationship was very weak. The t-statistic of -0.123 and the p-value of 0.904

suggested that this relationship was not statistically significant at all. The auditor's competence did not seem to have a significant impact on audit assurance in this analysis.

Overall, the multiple R-value of *0.525* suggested the independent variables (ethical practices and competence) and the dependent variable (audit assurance) had a moderate linear relationship. However, the r-squared value of *0.276* indicated that only about 27.6% of the variation in audit assurance could be explained by the independent variables in this model. Additionally, the f-value of *3.242* with a p-value of *0.064* gives an impression that the overall model may not be statistically significant at the *0.05* significance level which did not reject the null hypothesis (H_03), suggesting that ethical practices and competence of auditors did not have a significant effect on the audit assurance they provided.

DISCUSSION

1.The Extent that the Auditors Observed Ethical Practices

1.1. In terms of Integrity, auditors consistently exhibited a strong commitment to integrity in their professional dealings. They firmly adhered to high ethical standards and prioritized presenting audit information honestly and professionally. Auditors were resolute in not allowing their integrity to be questioned and were dedicated to maintaining trust with the public and audited entities. Their overall mean score of 4.76, which was interpreted as very extensive, reflected their unwavering commitment to integrity in their work.

The result implied that the higher the integrity that an auditor had, the better the audit quality would be. Auditors' integrity plays a significant role in audit quality, and they should strive to maintain their integrity. The most critical element affecting audit assurance concerning integrity was the way the auditors carried out their audit duties by upholding the principles of honesty, diligence, and reasonability. This result implied that integrity only reasonably accepted the errors that were unintentional and disagreements as it did not accept the principles of fraud or abolition. Auditors must always improve their knowledge since they were the ones who led the implementation of audit assignments to maximize the application of their knowledge in their practice.

Accordingly, this result was supported by the study of Setyowati et al. (2021), which concluded that the auditors' ethics affected the audit quality in a way to disclose things that according to their consideration and beliefs needed to be done when performing audit tasks in accordance with facts and maintained honesty and obeyed the rules in performing audit tasks. In addition, they stated that valid auditor ethics indicators come from integrity, objectivity, and independence.

1.2. In terms of Professional Competence and Due Care, auditors demonstrated a clear dedication to professional competence and due care as they exercised professional skepticism, followed technical standards diligently, and continually strived to enhance their skills and knowledge. Auditors asserted their competence and qualification for auditing services. With an overall mean score of 4.61 interpreted as very extensive, it was

evident that auditors prioritized upholding high standards of competence and due care in their roles.

Auditors prioritized maintaining their high levels of professional competence and due care in their roles. The result implied that auditors should be embodied with multiple approaches as their basis in deciding on what audit activities they should do. In addition, due professional care was the application of considerations in deciding the scope, the methodology to utilize, and the selection of auditing tests and procedures. It requires auditors to execute professional skepticism, specifically, the attitude of questioning and critically evaluating the audit evidence gathered. Therefore, professional competence and due care were indeed necessary in producing a high level of audit quality

The result was aligned with the conclusion of Kertarajasa et al. (2019) stating the high level of professional competence and due care could improve that quality of audit assurance.

1.3. In terms of Objectivity, auditors expressed a commitment to objectivity and impartiality in their work, although responses vary slightly in this section. They emphasized avoiding bias and undue influence, performed work with an objective mindset, and maintained fairness and intellectual honesty. However, there was room for improvement in avoiding conflicts of interest. The overall mean score of 4.48 interpreted as highly extensive suggested that auditors collectively value objectivity but may benefit from further attention to this aspect.

Being objective toward clients meant that an auditor fulfilled his professional obligations. The result implied that the extent to which auditors fairly presented audited financial statements in an audit report and avoided bias in discharging their responsibility influenced the audit assurance they provided. On the other hand, the desired audit results would be challenging to attain when an auditor colluded with a specific interest with the client or was not objective when conducting the interview.

The result was supported by the study of Lubis (2021) who concluded that objectivity had a positive effect on the quality of audit results, and auditors who were objective could highly make a balanced assessment of existing conditions without being influenced by their own interests or the interests of others in making decisions.

1.4. In terms of Professional Behavior, auditors prioritized professional behavior and ethical conduct in their interactions. They strongly complied with relevant laws and regulations and refrained from doing actions that could discredit their profession. Auditors also emphasized courtesy and consideration in their dealings during audits. While there was room for improvement in areas like appropriate dressing and avoiding profanity, the overall mean score of 4.49 interpreted as highly extensive. The overall mean result across all sections was 4.59 which was interpreted as very extensive indicating a strong agreement among auditors regarding their adherence to ethical practices in their profession.

The result implied that the auditors must be truthful to the management, company owners, creditors, and other parties who relied on audited financial statements in observing ethical practices in terms of professional behavior. Auditors were very concerned about the quality of the audit, an important assurance that they could fulfil their obligations to their

clients. Auditor ethics would have a great impact on audit quality and decision-making because auditors' compliance with codes of conduct and standards could reflect in their objectivity, professional behavior, and many more.

Accordingly, the result of this study was aligned with the study conducted by Adekoya et al. (2020) who concluded that the professional behavior of the auditors could be influenced in many aspects. It showed that professional behavior inherently defined the characteristics of the auditors in an audit firm which showed their behavior, especially in the execution of their responsibilities. Furthermore, the findings of the study suggested that respondents perceived to have a lot of influence on the behaviors of the auditors.

2. The Level of Competence of the Auditors

2.1. In terms of Transferable Skills, auditors displayed strong proficiency in skills such as updating deadlines based on changing circumstances and gathering information systematically. They excelled in clear communication and rapport-building. However, there was room for improvement in minimizing distractions. Overall, auditors exhibited a commendable level of competence in transferable skills, with a total mean of 4.24 which was interpreted as high, indicating their effectiveness in areas like time management and self-awareness.

The result implied that auditors had remarkable competency in a variety of transferable abilities. Auditors demonstrated a great sense of self-awareness, as seen by their capacity to reflect on and analyze their own performance. It also emphasized effective communication abilities, with auditors displaying the capacity to articulate themselves clearly and concisely to a group of individuals and create rapport with others.

The results strengthened the findings of Nambiar et al. (2019) and Mardan and Hussain (2023) who concluded that transferrable skills are crucial for individual's competencies in the workplace.

2.2. In terms of Audit Skills, the auditors demonstrated a remarkable proficiency in seeking information on the laws and regulations, studying the policies of the management, and validating the reliability of audit evidence. They also showed a strong understanding of the initial information of the cases to be audited, as well as a commitment to professional development through training. While some skills such as profiling the environment and the stakeholders received slightly lower ratings, the total mean for audit skills of 4.41 interpreted as high, indicating a high level of overall competence in the audit-specific abilities of the auditors. Considering both transferable and audit skills, auditors achieved an impressive overall mean result of 4.32, interpreted as high, indicating a high level of competence in audit-related skills demonstrated by auditors.

The result implied that the top-rated skills highlighted the auditors' commitment to staying informed and ensuring accuracy in their work. Auditors showed a strong understanding of the initial information of the case to be audited, indicating their ability to start the audit process effectively. Therefore, the high level of competence in audit-related skills

demonstrated by auditors emphasized their effectiveness in conducting audits and maintaining compliance and accountability within audited entities

The result aligned with the study conducted by Alsughayer (2021) and Pinto et al. (2020) which proved the existence of a correlation between the auditor's competence on auditing and the audit quality they provided.

3. The Level of Audit Assurance Provided by the Auditor in an Audit

The level of audit assurance provided by the auditor in the audited financial statements was prepared in accordance with auditing standards and principles and attained the highest weighted mean of *4.80*, interpreted as very high. The level of audit assurance provided by the auditor in an audit obtained an overall mean of *4.65*, interpreted as very high.

The result implied that the increasing level of audit assurance of auditors reduced the information risk about the client which had a significant effect on the decision-making of the financial statements users. Consequently, the auditors' opinion was not absolute but their opinion enhanced the value and usefulness of the financial statements by expressing that these were fairly presented. Hence, the higher level of assurance to the financial statements guaranteed the users that the financial statements were reliable.

The result of this study was supported by the study conducted by Tarmidi et al. (2019) which indicated that external parties, particularly the auditors, were the ones who conducted high-quality audits and rendered high-quality audit reports as they were not subject to the influence of management. Therefore, the findings highlighted the importance of independence and objectivity in the audit process. This ensured that the judgment of the auditors remained untainted by external influences as stakeholders relied on audit reports provided by auditors, which were based on an objective examination of audit facts and findings and it protected and preserved the interests of stakeholders.

4. Significant Relationship Between the Extent of the Ethical Practices of Auditors and the Level of Audit Assurance

The analysis investigated the connection between the ethical practices of auditors and the level of audit assurance they offered. The results indicated a statistically significant positive correlation ($R\text{-value} = 0.525$, $p\text{-value} = 0.018$) between the extent of ethical practices and audit assurance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected, which suggested that ethical practices and audit assurance had a significant relationship.

The result implied that the ethical conduct of the auditors ensured that the audit assurance was credible and reliable. Auditors were more likely to deliver a high-quality audit assurance if they prioritized their ethical practices. The result highlighted that adhering to ethical practices was not merely an obligation as it could positively benefit the audit quality since adhering to ethical practices minimized the potential for bias or manipulation leading to a more accurate assessment of financial statements and a higher level of confidence in the audit opinion. Consequently, it became crucial to establish strong ethical guidelines to guarantee that ethical practices were instilled within their professional conduct.

The result of this study was aligned with the findings of the study conducted by Alkebeese et al. (2021) who found a correlation between the audit quality and auditors' professional

ethics. In addition, Haeridistia and Fadjarenie (2019) had similar findings in their study. According to them, the audit results would likely be similar to the actual financial statements of the audited entity if the auditors always adhered to the professional code of conduct when they did the audit process.

5. Significant Relationship Between the Level Competence of Auditors and the Level of Audit Assurance

The researchers explored the relationship between auditor competence and the level of audit assurance they provided. The statistical analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant relationship (R-value = 0.394, p-value = 0.086) between auditor competence and audit assurance. As a result, the null hypothesis (H_0) was not rejected, indicating that auditor competence did not significantly impact the level of audit assurance.

The result explained that the competence of the auditor did not have a significant impact on the level of audit assurance. Auditors were expected to have excellent competency in carrying out their duties, however, the competency of the auditor was not necessarily needed when the supervision of the superiors during the audit process was good as well as when the system implemented was good. Hence, whether the auditor was competent or not, the quality of the audit would still be the same.

Consequently, this result was supported by the findings of the study by Putri and Nengzih (2021) and Kusumawati and Syamsuddin (2018) who gave a verdict that there the competence of the auditor did not have a significant effect on the quality of audit assurance. In contrast, the presented study was not in line with the result of the study by Ramlah et al. (2018) and Pinto et al. (2020) which stated that the competence of the auditor affected the quality of the audit.

6. Significant Influence Ethical Practices and Competence of Auditors had Effect on the Audit Assurance

The results of the statistical analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship between ethical practices and audit assurance but it was not statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. Auditor competence did not appear to significantly affect the audit assurance, and this relationship was also not statistically significant. Overall, the model explains only 27.6% of the variation in audit assurance. The null hypothesis (H_0) was not rejected, indicating that ethical practices and auditors' competence did not significantly impact the level of audit assurance. The analysis suggested that further research may be needed to draw more definitive conclusions about the impact of these factors on audit assurance.

The result was in connection with the findings of Ramlah et al. (2018) who concluded that the interaction of competence with auditor ethics on audit quality had a negative effect on the quality of the audit implying that auditors with a low level of competence could still provide the same or even better audit quality compared to the auditors with a very high level of competence, as long as the former did their audit tasks while adhering the ethical standards. This was because auditors with a high level of competence, in terms of knowledge and experience, likely showed a highly selfish attitude by ignoring the standard

operating procedures oftentimes in carrying out the audit process, even being less cautious, which led to a not good audit quality.

This result was the same as the findings of Kertarajasa et al. (2019) stating that auditor ethics and competence did not have a significant effect on audit quality. However, this study did not support the findings of Asry (2021), who concluded that the competence and ethics of auditors had a simultaneous effect on the audit quality. Further research with a larger sample size or different methodologies may be needed to draw more robust conclusions about the impact of these factors on audit assurance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were hereby made:

1. The study concluded that the auditors extensively observed ethical practices, in terms of integrity, objectivity, professional competence and due care, and professional behavior. The auditors' ethics had a great impact on audit quality and decision-making because auditors' compliance with codes of conduct and standards was reflected in the indicators therewith.
2. The study concluded that the auditors had a high level of competence in terms of their transferrable and audit skills. Therefore, the high level of competence of auditors emphasized their effectiveness in conducting audits.
3. The study concluded that auditors provided a very high level of audit assurance. Hence, the high level of assurance of the audited financial statements guarantees a reliable financial statement for its users.
4. The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between ethical practices and audit assurance. This meant that the ethical practices of auditors played a vital role in influencing audit assurance.
5. The study concluded that there was no significant relationship between the auditors' competence and their audit assurance. This suggested that auditor competence, as measured in this study, did not appear to be a determining factor in shaping audit assurance.
6. The study concluded that both the ethical practices and competence of auditors did not have a statistically significant effect on the audit assurance they provided. This suggested that there could be other factors that were not considered in this analysis which could also have played a crucial role in determining the level of audit assurance that the auditors provided.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusion arrived in the study, the following were recommended:

1. Auditing firms may prioritize and enhance their ethical practices. This may include implementing and promoting a strong ethical code of conduct, providing ongoing ethics

training for auditors, and maintaining transparency in all audit processes. By doing so, auditing firms may improve their reputation and strengthen trust and confidence.

2. Businesses may prioritize selecting professional competent auditors with a strong track record of adherence to the code of ethics. Stakeholders, including shareholders and creditors, may actively monitor the ethical practices of auditors when evaluating the reliability of financial statements. Engaging auditors with a proven commitment to ethics may enhance transparency and trust in financial reporting.

3. The Institution may actively support the activities of the students that may help them gain insights and understanding about the importance of being a competent professional who complies with ethical standards. With this, the institution may produce competent auditors who adhere to the ethical code of conduct contributing to the auditing profession positively.

4. The Department, supported by the Institution, may conduct seminars and events that provide necessary knowledge and skills to the business students as a whole. Furthermore, the Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA) program of this department may be focused on the factors highlighting the importance of the auditing profession in our society by conducting studies regarding this subject matter.

5. Researchers in the field of auditing may continue to explore the dynamics between ethical practices, competence, and audit assurance. Further research may delve into the specific mechanisms through which ethical practices and competence influence audit quality. Additionally, researchers may explore how different training programs and interventions impacted auditors' ethics and competence.

6. Future studies in the realm of auditing may consider expanding the scope to include qualitative research, such as in-depth interviews. This may deepen the understanding of the factors influencing auditors' ethical decisions and competence. Moreover, examining the impact of regulatory changes and industry trends on ethical practices and audit quality may offer valuable insights for both academics and practitioners.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this study, the researchers ensured that the respondents had informed choice about whether to participate in this study. The researchers secured an informed consent from the respondents before conducting the study. Also, the researchers discussed with the respondents the objective of this study and asked if they had concerns before handing them the survey questionnaires.

The researchers refrained from forcing the respondents to participate in answering the questionnaire. The researchers informed the respondents that their engagement in the study was voluntary. When a respondent chose not to participate in answering the questionnaires, the researchers asked the reason for the refusal and addressed the

situation respectfully. Nonetheless, when the respondents wished to withdraw from participating in this study, they could freely do so at any time.

The researchers ensured the confidentiality of the respondent's personal information. Concerning the participants' anonymity, they were given the choice of disclosing or not their names on the survey questionnaire. Information was obtained without collecting any sensitive information or personal information that could jeopardize the security of the respondents, and the researchers assured that the data gathered was used solely for the study. The researchers made sure that there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings, no conflict of interest existed in conducting the study, and the results were purely used for research purposes only.

Acknowledgments

The researchers extend their heartfelt gratitude to all who contributed to the realization of this study. First and foremost, gratitude is offered to our Almighty God for providing the researchers with strength, wisdom, and guidance throughout their research journey. To Dr. Cliff Kirl F. Lubon, CPA, your unwavering support and permission to conduct this study are deeply appreciated. Prof. Czarina Alexandria P. Wata, your patience and guidance were invaluable throughout the research process. Dr. Lily Grace M. Morales, LPT, your mentorship allowed us to grow and learn through this experience.

Special thanks to Dr. Haya Jane E. Elan, LPT, and Prof. Cynthia Marie L. Hilado, MBA, for your thorough examination and constructive feedback, which enhanced the credibility of this study. To all respondents, your active cooperation was indispensable in making this research successful.

To our families, your endless support both financially and emotionally sustained us through every challenge. You have been our unwavering inspiration and motivation to strive for excellence.

To everyone mentioned, and to those whose contributions may not be explicitly stated but are equally valued, this study would not have been possible without your selfless dedication and assistance. Your collective efforts have truly made a difference.

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